

SIMILE IS A TYPE OF METAPHOR

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The roots of metaphor as a notion take us back more than 2000 years. The origin of the term is assigned to Aristotle and is connected to his understanding of art as imitation of life. From Greek the word –metaphor translates as –transfer . The definition of metaphor by Aristotle is as follows:

Metaphor is the application of an alien name by transference either from genus to species, or from species to genus, or from species to species, or by analogy, that is, proportion.[1]

In other words, Aristotle’s metaphor is a comparison of two things which are alien, or unrelated, to each other. It is a conceptual phenomenon which is a result of manipulation of different types. It was also Aristotle who was the first to emphasize the importance of mastering metaphor for becoming a great public speaker. In his Poetics we read:

...the greatest thing by far is to have a command of metaphor. This alone cannot be imparted by another; it is the mark of genius, for to make good metaphors implies an eye for resemblances. [2]

Aristotle, the forefather of metaphor as a concept, laid the foundation for a powerful tradition of metaphor which has been dominating for thousands of years. This tradition is known as classic. It rests on type hierarchy (genus to species, species to genus, etc.) and views metaphor not as a part of everyday human communication, but rather as a privilege of public speakers.

Aristotle’s, or the classic, view of metaphor as a device reserved for rhetoric was finally challenged by George Lakoff and Mark Johnson in 1980. In their shared work *Metaphors we live by* they treat metaphor as being part of daily language and thought. This approach to metaphor has become known as the cognitive approach. Sometimes it is also referred to as the modern approach.

In a way Lakoff and Johnson’s work is a Copernican turn in the theory of metaphor as it has changed the focus from metaphor as a property of words to metaphor as the property of concepts. It means that metaphors are not only literary patterns but ways in which we perceive the world around us. Lakoff and Johnson were brought together by the common interest in metaphor and quickly

discovered that they both found the traditional views of metaphor unsatisfactory. Johnson for one had obtained evidence that metaphor is widely used in everyday life and thought of ordinary people, not just of those for whom the art of writing or giving public speeches is a profession. Thus, their major argument is that the process of human thinking is largely metaphorical in itself.

By changing the focus of how metaphor is viewed, Lakoff and Johnson at the same time expanded its definition – it has become more than just a figure of speech. They have convincingly proved that metaphor is integrated in the speakers' perception of the world.

All in all, their theory of conceptual, or cognitive, metaphors rests on the following arguments:[3]

- 1) metaphors are a part of everyday life, thought and experience;
- 2) metaphors are an inevitable and unconscious part of the process of human thinking;
- 3) metaphors provide a foundation for our conceptual system, it is a property of concepts rather than words;
- 4) metaphors are widely used in the life of ordinary people, most of the time without them even noticing it;
- 5) abstract concepts, such as love, argument, idea etc., are incomplete without metaphor even though they have a literal core.

In their work Lakoff and Johnson categorize conceptual metaphors (which are, following their approach, represented by capital letters in the present work) as structural, orientational and ontological. They speak of structural metaphors when –one concept is metaphorically structured in terms of another[4]. For example, we can comprehend an aspect of arguing in terms of battle: Your claims are indefensible; He attacked every weak point in my argument; His criticisms were right on target etc.

The simile that describes the resemblance between two dissimilar things, usually flagging up the comparison with “as” or “like,” has been a literary device to lend color to the English language since time immemorial. Musical theater legend Oscar Hammerstein was a master “similist,” often piling on his vivid comparisons for added effect. “A Wonderful Guy,” from the classic South Pacific, expanded on the famous “I’m corny as Kansas in August / I’m as normal as blueberry pie” with

“I’m as trite and as gay as a daisy in May” and “I’m bromidic and bright / As a moon-happy night / Pourin’ light on the dew!”

Its effectiveness for expressing thoughts more clearly and vividly makes the simile one of most widely used figures of speech in written and spoken English. Similes crop up in newspaper and magazine articles, fiction and nonfiction, dramas as well as daily conversations. The ones with the most zip tend to metamorphose into common expressions that are used unchanged or refreshed. In the age of sound bites and tweets they are more than ever timely and, to borrow an ever-popular simile, useful as a Swiss army knife for drawing pithy word sketches that are more robust than a single word and more spontaneous than a formal quote.[5].

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